

RESEARCH

Performance Analysis of Feedback-Free Collision Resolution NDMA Protocol

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Abstract

To support communications of a large number of deployed devices while guaranteeing limited signaling load, low energy consumption, and high reliability, future cellular systems require efficient random access protocols. However, how to address the collision resolution at the receiver is still the main bottleneck of these protocols. The network-assisted diversity multiple access (NDMA) protocol solves the issue and attains the highest potential throughput at the cost of keeping devices active to acquire feedback and repeating transmissions until successful decoding. In contrast, another potential approach is the feedback-free NDMA (FF-NDMA) protocol, in which devices do not repeat packets in a predefined number of consecutive time slots without waiting for feedback associated to repetitions. Here, we investigate the FF-NDMA protocol from a cellular network perspective in order to elucidate under what circumstances this scheme is more energy efficient than NDMA. We characterize analytically the FF-NDMA protocol along with the multipacket reception model and a finite Markov chain. Analytic expressions for throughput, delay, capture probability, energy, and energy efficiency are derived. Then, clues for system design are established according to the different trade-offs studied. Simulation results show that FF-NDMA is more energy efficient than classical NDMA and HARQ-NDMA at low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and at medium SNR when the load increases.

Keywords: slotted random access; packet repetition; multipacket reception; feedback-free NDMA; energy efficiency

1 Introduction

The fifth generation (5G) of cellular networks, set for availability around 2020, is expected to enable a fully mobile and connected society, characterized by a massive growth in connectivity and an increased density and volume of traffic. Hence, a wide range of requirements arise, such as scalability, rapid programmability, high capacity, security, reliability, availability, low latency, and long-life battery for devices [1].

All these requirements pave the way for machine-type communications (MTC),

¹which enable the implementation of the Internet of Things (IoT) [2]. Unlike typ-¹
²ical human-to-human communications, MTC devices are equipped with batteries²
³of finite lifetime and generate bursty and automatic data without or with low hu-³
⁴man intervention, so that traffic in the uplink direction is accentuated [3]. MTC⁴
⁵systems consider different use cases that range from massive MTC, where the num-⁵
⁶ber of deployed devices is very high, to mission-critical MTC, where real-time and⁶
⁷high-reliability communication needs have to be satisfied [4]. ⁷

⁸To address such a massive number of low-powered devices generating bursty traf-⁸
⁹fic with low latency requirements, simple medium access control (MAC)-layer ran-⁹
¹⁰dom access protocols of ALOHA-type are preferred because they offer a relatively¹⁰
¹¹straightforward implementation and can accommodate bursty devices in a shared¹¹
¹²communication channel [4, 5]. They are indeed used in today's most advanced cel-¹²
¹³lular networks (as the random access channel (RACH) in LTE) [6] and are being¹³
¹⁴considered in different MTC systems, such as LoRa [7], SigFox, enhanced MTC [8],¹⁴
¹⁵narrowband (NB) LTE-M [9, 10], and NB-IoT [11–13]. ¹⁵

¹⁶Basic ALOHA-type protocols are based on the collision model: a packet is re-¹⁶
¹⁷ceived error free only when a single device transmits. Thus, the MAC layer and the¹⁷
¹⁸physical (PHY) layer are fully decoupled. In [14], Guez *et al.* made a fundamen-¹⁸
¹⁹tal change in the collision model and introduced the *multipacket reception* (MPR)¹⁹
²⁰model: when there are simultaneous transmissions, instead of associating collisions²⁰
²¹to deterministic failures, reception is described by conditional probabilities. There-²¹
²²fore, signal processing techniques enable a receiver to decode simultaneous signals²²
²³from different devices and hence collisions can be resolved at the PHY layer. As a²³
²⁴result, a tighter interaction between PHY and MAC layers is achieved [14–16]. ²⁴

²⁵MPR can be realized through many techniques, which are classified according to²⁵
²⁶three different perspectives: *transmitter*, *trans-receiver*, and *receiver* (see [17] for²⁶
²⁷details). Among all of them, a promising trans-receiver approach based on random²⁷
²⁸access for different 5G services is the *Network-assisted Diversity Multiple Access*²⁸
²⁹(NDMA) protocol. NDMA was initially presented in [18] for flat-fading channels²⁹
³⁰and, afterwards, extended to multi-path time-dispersive channels in [19]. The basic³⁰
³¹idea of NDMA is that the signals received in collided transmissions are stored in³¹
³²memory and then they are combined with future repetitions at the receiver so as³²
³³to extract all collided packets with a linear detector. In the single-antenna case³³
³⁴and under the assumption of perfect reception, NDMA only requires the number³⁴
³⁵of repetitions to be equal to the number of collided packets [18]. Thus, NDMA³⁵
³⁶dramatically enhances throughput and delay performance as compared to ALOHA-³⁶
³⁷type protocols, but estimation of the number of devices involved in a collision (e.g.³⁷

¹ P devices) and a properly adjustment of the number of repetitions (i.e. $P-1$) is¹
²required every time a collision occurs. 2

³ Many NDMA protocols, and variations of it, have been proposed and analyzed in³
⁴the literature, including different ways to determine the number of devices involved⁴
⁵in a collision [18–22], interference cancellation receivers [23–25], and modified pro-⁵
⁶ocols that use channel knowledge at the transmitter side [26,27]. Stability analysis⁶
⁷of NDMA was addressed in [28–30]. Finally, the hybrid automatic repeat request⁷
⁸(HARQ) concept was applied to NDMA in [31] (named H-NDMA) in order to deal⁸
⁹with reception errors at low/medium SNR by forcing devices involved in a collision⁹
¹⁰of P devices to transmit repetitions more than $P-1$ times. This way, packet recep-¹⁰
¹¹tion was significantly improved at low SNR with H-NDMA as compared to classical¹¹
¹²NDMA. 12

¹³ One of the main drawbacks of NDMA protocols is, however, the overhead required¹³
¹⁴to identify collisions and adjust the number of repetitions accordingly every time a¹⁴
¹⁵collision occurs (which implies communicating it to all the devices involved in the¹⁵
¹⁶collision) [18]. Indeed, devices need to decode control signaling at every time slot to¹⁶
¹⁷know if the subsequent time slot is reserved for repetitions or not, hence increasing¹⁷
¹⁸the energy consumption. This aspect is critical for MTC devices with finite battery¹⁸
¹⁹lifetime. 19

²⁰ To cope with these issues, authors in [32] proposed a non-centralized procedure²⁰
²¹for NDMA, coined *Feedback-Free NDMA* (FF-NDMA), in which the number of time²¹
²²slots for repetitions is kept constant to R (conforming a contention period (CP))²²
²³and is equal for all devices and transmissions. See Fig. 1 for $R=3$. Accordingly,²³
²⁴devices are only allowed to start transmission at the beginning of the CP and²⁴
²⁵will do so R times. This way, collisions of up to R devices can be resolved in the²⁵
²⁶single antenna case without requiring the receiver to communicate the collision²⁶
²⁷multiplicity to the devices every time a collision occurs and avoiding the signaling²⁷
²⁸related to the state (reserved for repetitions or not) of the subsequent time slot. The²⁸
²⁹joint PHY-MAC performance analysis of FF-NDMA protocol was performed in [33]²⁹
³⁰for the general case of MIMO systems^[1] with orthogonal space-time block coding³⁰
³¹(OSTBC). Significant throughput and energy gains as compared to ALOHA-based³¹
³²schemes were reported with a non-centralized protocol that requires low overhead.³²
³³Nevertheless, it was assumed in [32,33] that whenever a packet was received in error³³
³⁴at the receiver then said packet was lost, since FF-NDMA was initially designed to³⁴
³⁵address the broadcast protocol in ad hoc networks where no feedback is available.³⁵
³⁶36

³⁷^[1]All previous works on NDMA have focused on single-input single-output (SISO) and single-input³⁷
³⁷multiple output (SIMO) systems rather than in the general MIMO case. 37

¹ Although NDMA and FF-NDMA were initially proposed a decade ago, the emerg-
² ing MTC systems (with different requirements than those of conventional human-
³ based cellular networks) suggest reviewing random access protocols with MPR and³
⁴ analyzing its applicability to the uplink communication in cellular networks [3],⁴
⁵ specially for scenarios characterized by a large number of devices, limited signal-
⁶ ing load, low energy consumption, and high reliability. In particular, NDMA-based⁶
⁷ protocols are highly attractive for massive MTC. NDMA has been deeply analyzed⁷
⁸ in the recent literature with different protocols (e.g. H-NDMA [31]). However, FF-⁸
⁹ NDMA misses such wide analysis while it is suitable for massive MTC scenarios due⁹
¹⁰ to its low associated signaling load and reduced implementation complexity. Indeed,¹⁰
¹¹ it is worth mentioning that NB-IoT [11] and the New Radio (NR) access technology¹¹
¹² design for 3GPP 5G systems [34] already consider a contention-based transmission¹²
¹³ mode with a predefined number of packet repetitions (known as uplink grant-free¹³
¹⁴ access, in which devices contend for resources, and multiple predefined repetitions¹⁴
¹⁵ are allowed, as specified in [34]). Such uplink grant-free access in NR targets at least¹⁵
¹⁶ for massive MTC, and would allow the implementation of FF-NDMA. ¹⁶

¹⁷ In this paper, we analyze the FF-NDMA protocol with MIMO configurations ¹⁷
¹⁸ and OSTBC from a cellular network perspective, in which multiple devices intend ¹⁸
¹⁹ to communicate with a base station (BS), as shown in Fig 1. The MIMO system ¹⁹
²⁰ defined and analyzed in the sequel carries over to a multi-cell scenario where cell- ²⁰
²¹ edge terminals experience similar average SNR to an x -number of BSs that are ²¹
²² able to receive and decode packets in a distributed way with an x -fold number of ²²
²³ receive antennas. Differently from [32,33], in which no feedback was considered and ²³
²⁴ whenever a packet was received in error then the packet was discarded, we use a ²⁴
²⁵ general model in which packets are not discarded. To do so, we consider a finite-user ²⁵
²⁶ slotted random access system where devices can be either transmitting, thinking (i.e. ²⁶
²⁷ there is no packet to transmit), decoding, or backlogged (i.e. packet transmission ²⁷
²⁸ was erroneous and the device is waiting for a new transmission opportunity) and we ²⁸
²⁹ assume that each device is equipped with a single packet buffer^[2]. Therefore, FF- ²⁹
³⁰ NDMA is feedback-free in the sense that it is not needed to broadcast information ³⁰
³¹ related to the number of repetitions and to the state of the forthcoming time slots (as ³¹
³² in NDMA or H-NDMA) but, in contrast to [32,33], ACK feedback to acknowledge ³²
³³ a correct detection of the devices' packets per CP is assumed. ³³

³⁴ In this context, the main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows: ³⁴
³⁵

³⁶ ^[2]The single packet buffer assumption is useful to emulate MTC scenarios where packets are ³⁶
³⁷ generated every certain period of time (e.g. by sensors) and in which a single packet buffer is ³⁷
³⁷ enough to report the latest information.

- 1 • we develop a joint PHY-MAC analysis of the FF-NDMA protocol by using¹
 2 the MPR model and, then, characterize the system through a finite Markov²
 3 chain, for which the system state probabilities and the transition probabilities³
 4 among them are obtained in closed-form. 4
- 5 • we characterize analytically the FF-NDMA protocol in terms of throughput,⁵
 6 delay, capture probability (i.e. probability of a successful transmission or,⁶
 7 equivalently, reliability of the protocol), energy, and energy efficiency (i.e.⁷
 8 efficiency of the protocol, which is measured through a throughput-energy⁸
 9 ratio). Also, we propose two criteria to analyze the stability of finite-user⁹
 10 random access with single packet buffer^[3]. 10
- 11 • we investigate the system performance of FF-NDMA as a function of the CP¹¹
 12 length (R), for different SNR and load conditions, and we compare FF-NDMA¹²
 13 with S-ALOHA, classical NDMA [18], and H-NDMA^[4] [31]. As we will see, the¹³
 14 energy consumption is reduced with FF-NDMA as compared to H-NDMA in¹⁴
 15 certain situations due to the lower control signaling to be decoded. To address¹⁵
 16 the throughput-energy trade-off, we use the energy efficiency metric and focus¹⁶
 17 on determining the circumstances in which FF-NDMA is *more energy efficient*¹⁷
 18 than H-NDMA. 18

19 *Organization:* The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we assess the differ-¹⁹
 20 ences between FF-NDMA and other NDMA-based protocols (including NDMA and²⁰
 21 H-NDMA) and then we present the system model and the main features of the FF-²¹
 22 NDMA protocol. Section 3 establishes the MPR model and characterizes the system²²
 23 by using a finite Markov chain, for which the system state probabilities (related to²³
 24 the backlog state) are derived. Then, in Section 4, based on the obtained system²⁴
 25 state probabilities, expressions for throughput, delay, capture probability, energy,²⁵
 26 and energy efficiency are developed and two stability conditions are set. Section 5²⁶
 27 presents the simulation results by using different SNR and different offered loads²⁷
 28 and system design clues are extracted. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 6.²⁸

29 *Notation:* In this paper, scalars are denoted by italic letters. Boldface lower-case²⁹
 30 and upper-case letters denote vectors and matrices, respectively. For given real-³⁰
 31 valued scalars a and b , $\Pr(a \leq b)$, $\Pr(a = b)$, $\Pr(a = b | \mathcal{C})$, $\lceil a \rceil$, and $\log_2(a)$, denote the³¹
 32 probability of a being smaller than b , the probability of a being equal to b , the³²
 33 probability of a being equal to b given condition \mathcal{C} , the ceiling function of a , and the³³
 34 ³⁴

³⁵[3] Stability has been defined in literature for infinite-user as well as for infinite-buffer systems, but³⁵
 not for finite-user single-buffer systems.

³⁶[4] We compare FF-NDMA not only with NDMA but also with H-NDMA, since H-NDMA signif-³⁶
 icantly outperforms NDMA at low SNR regimes (i.e., the common operational range for MTC³⁷
 devices that use low order constellations).³⁷

¹base 2 logarithm of a , respectively. For given positive integer scalars a and b , $\binom{a}{b}$ ²
³refers to the binomial coefficient and $a!$ denotes the factorial of a . For a given vector³
⁴ \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{a}^T stands for the vector transpose. $\mathcal{Q}(\cdot)$ refers to the Q-function (i.e. the integral⁴
⁵of a Gaussian density). $\mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $\mathbb{R}_+^{m \times n}$, and $\mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$ denote an m by n dimensional real⁵
⁶space, real positive space, and complex space, respectively. 6

⁷2 System Model 7

⁸In this section we first compare FF-NDMA protocol with classical NDMA [18] and 8
⁹H-NDMA [31], and then present the system model for FF-NDMA. 9
¹⁰10

¹¹2.1 Comparison of NDMA Protocols 11

¹²Fig. 2 shows the protocol differences between NDMA^[5] and FF-NDMA with $R=3$.¹² 12
¹³To perform a fair protocol comparison we assume that each time slot contains a¹³
¹⁴data part for data transmission and a control part for feedback from BS (which is¹⁴
¹⁵not always used in FF-NDMA). 15

¹⁶In FF-NDMA, transmissions are attempted at the CP start and the number of¹⁶
¹⁷repetitions is fixed to the CP length (R repetitions) independently of the number¹⁷
¹⁸of devices that collide. In contrast, in NDMA, transmissions are attempted at the¹⁸
¹⁹time slot scale and the number of repetitions is dynamically adapted according to¹⁹
²⁰the number of collided packets. H-NDMA follows classical NDMA operation but,²⁰
²¹at low/medium SNR, the BS might ask for additional repetitions on a HARQ basis²¹
²²to improve packet reception. For these reasons, the throughput of FF-NDMA can²²
²³not be as large as that of classical NDMA at high SNR and as that of H-NDMA at²³
²⁴any SNR range. However, load signaling, implementation complexity, and energy²⁴
²⁵consumption are reduced with FF-NDMA. 25

²⁶Under NDMA, receiving and decoding control signaling from the BS is required at²⁶
²⁷every time slot for different purposes: to know if the subsequent time slot is either²⁷
²⁸busy or free (i.e. reserved for repetitions of collided packets or not), to receive ACK²⁸
²⁹in case a packet was transmitted, and to know the number of repetitions to be²⁹
³⁰performed in case a packet was transmitted but not successfully decoded due to³⁰
³¹collision [18]. H-NDMA requires extra signaling load from the BS towards devices³¹
³²to request additional repetitions on a HARQ basis [31], once the repetitions of³²
³³NDMA have been completed. On the other hand, in FF-NDMA, control signaling³³
³⁴is only needed to receive ACK at those CPs in which a packet was transmitted. This³⁴
³⁵makes the application of FF-NDMA to MTC systems highly attractive because the³⁵
³⁶energy consumption for control signaling decoding is reduced. The difference in the³⁶

³⁷^[5]H-NDMA matches NDMA operation in Fig. 2 under high SNR regime. 37

¹control signaling to be decoded with FF-NDMA and NDMA is illustrated in Fig. 2¹
²in orange color. 2

³ To summarize, the throughput of FF-NDMA is going to be lower than the³
⁴throughput of H-NDMA, but the energy consumption can be reduced with FF-⁴
⁵NDMA. In this line, in Section 5.2, we use the energy efficiency as a suitable met-⁵
⁶ric to address the throughput-energy trade-offs between FF-NDMA and H-NDMA⁶
⁷and, hence, determine which protocol is more energy efficient under different cir-⁷
⁸cumstances. 8

⁹ In addition, due to the lower control signaling to be decoded with FF-NDMA,⁹
¹⁰its implementation complexity is also significantly reduced as compared to NDMA¹⁰
¹¹or H-NDMA, because devices do not need to decode control signaling from the BS¹¹
¹²at every time slot and can enter into sleep mode. With FF-NDMA, decoding of a¹²
¹³single control signaling per CP in which transmission was attempted is required.¹³
¹⁴With NDMA or H-NDMA, decoding of control signaling at every time slot while¹⁴
¹⁵data is in the buffer is needed to know if transmission can be attempted and to get¹⁵
¹⁶the feedback. 16

¹⁷ Finally, it is important to emphasize that NDMA and H-NDMA require a self-¹⁷
¹⁸contained time slot, as shown in Fig. 2, in which the feedback for repetitions is¹⁸
¹⁹received just after the packet transmission and devices can attempt a repetition at¹⁹
²⁰the subsequent time slot. However, conventional repetitions processes (e.g. HARQ)²⁰
²¹might take some time slots between obtaining the feedback and retransmitting²¹
²²again [35]. In this situation, FF-NDMA avoids the additional delay that appears²²
²³in NDMA and H-NDMA under non-ideal repetition processes owing to the fact²³
²⁴that FF-NDMA does not rely on feedback to perform repetitions. Both the energy²⁴
²⁵savings (due to lower control signaling to decode) and the delay reductions (under²⁵
²⁶non-ideal repetition processes) are evaluated in Section 5.1. 26

²⁷ 27 ²⁸2.2 System Model for FF-NDMA 28

²⁹Consider a wireless cellular system composed of one BS with N receive antennas²⁹
³⁰and a deployment of K devices that will transmit packets to the BS through a³⁰
³¹slotted random access network, as shown in Fig. 1. Every device is equipped with³¹
³² M transmit antennas and has a single packet buffer. 32

³³ A frame composed of time slots is adopted. Each time slot contains a data part³³
³⁴for data transmission from devices to BS and a control part for feedback from³⁴
³⁵BS to devices (which is not always used), see Fig. 2. Time slots are grouped into³⁵
³⁶contention periods (CPs) of R time slots. We assume that each device is CP- and³⁶
³⁷slot-synchronous with the BS. Devices transmit whenever they have a packet in³⁷

¹their buffer at the beginning of the CP and packet repetitions are performed during¹
²the CP, so that devices transmit their packets R times using the data plane. After²
³the R repetitions, the BS acknowledges reception of the correctly received packets³
⁴through the control channel, so that devices know if transmission was successful or⁴
⁵not. Note that the maximum number of packets that can be simultaneously decoded⁵
⁶at a BS with N antennas and R repetitions is $\tilde{R}=NR$.⁶

⁷ In this scenario, collisions come up and every device can be in one of four different⁷
⁸device states: *thinking*, *transmitting*, *decoding*, or *backlogged*. The device state dia-⁸
⁹gram is shown in Fig. 3. In the thinking state, the device does not have a packet in⁹
¹⁰its buffer and does not participate in any scheduling activity. In this device state, a¹⁰
¹¹device generates a packet with probability σ . Once a packet is generated, its trans-¹¹
¹²mission is attempted at the beginning of the next CP and repeated during R time¹²
¹³slots (which corresponds to the transmitting state). After transmission, the device¹³
¹⁴decodes an acknowledgment of receipt message from the BS. If the transmission¹⁴
¹⁵succeeds (i.e. ACK feedback is received), the device remains in the thinking state.¹⁵
¹⁶Otherwise, the device moves into the backlogged state and retransmits the packet¹⁶
¹⁷with probability ν . When the packet is finally successfully decoded at the BS, the¹⁷
¹⁸device moves back to the thinking state and the process restarts again.¹⁸

¹⁹ We follow classical NDMA [18] and H-NDMA [31] assumption that uniform av-¹⁹
²⁰erage power from every device is received at the BS. This is possible thanks to the²⁰
²¹uplink slow power control mechanism [36]. Accordingly, all devices are received at²¹
²²the BS with the same average SNR (γ). The use of uplink power control has the²²
²³benefit that the scenario is terminal-wise symmetric (in terms of average SNR) and²³
²⁴the MPR model can be thus applied, as it will be shown in Section 3.²⁴

²⁷2.2.1 Signal Model²⁷

²⁸To exploit transmit diversity with no channel knowledge at the terminal side^[6],²⁸
²⁹transmission of each device is done through an OSTBC with Q complex symbols²⁹
³⁰that are spread in time and space over T channel uses and M transmit antennas.³⁰
³¹Therefore, the transmitted signal matrix for the k -th device, $\mathbf{X}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times T}$, is expressed³¹
³²as [37]:³²

$$\mathbf{X}_k = \sum_{q=1}^Q \alpha_{k,q} \mathbf{A}_q + j \beta_{k,q} \mathbf{B}_q, \quad (1)$$

³⁶
³⁷^[6]We assume that antenna precoding at the transmitter side entails additional complexity and energy consumption at the base band processing.³⁷

¹where $\alpha_{k,q}$ and $\beta_{k,q}$ refer to the real and imaginary parts of the q -th complex symbol¹
²at the k -th device, respectively, and $\mathbf{A}_q, \mathbf{B}_q \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times T}$ denote the pair of real-valued²
³code matrices that define the OSTBC [38]. We assume that the transmitted symbols³
⁴are m -QAM^[7].⁴

⁵ Considering a flat fading channel constant over the time slot and that \tilde{k} devices⁵
⁶are transmitting, the received signal at the N antennas of the BS over T channel⁶
⁷uses in the r -th time slot, $\mathbf{Y}_r \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times T}$, is given by [39]:⁷
⁸

$$\mathbf{Y}_r = \sum_{k=1}^{\tilde{k}} \sqrt{\frac{P_k}{ML_k}} \mathbf{H}_{k,r} \mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{W}_r, \quad (2)$$

¹¹ where P_k stands for the transmitted power of the k -th device, L_k refers to the¹¹
¹²slow propagation losses (including pathloss and shadowing) between the k -th device¹²
¹³and the BS, $\mathbf{H}_{k,r} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ is the Rayleigh flat-fading channel matrix between the¹³
¹⁴antennas at the k -th device and the BS during the r -th time slot that contains zero¹⁴
¹⁵mean complex Gaussian components, and $\mathbf{W}_r \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times T}$ denotes the received noise¹⁵
¹⁶that is composed of zero mean complex Gaussian components with variance σ_w^2 .¹⁶
¹⁷The average received SNR is given by $\gamma = \frac{P_k}{L_k \sigma_w^2}$ and is uniform among devices due¹⁷
¹⁸to the uplink slow power control mechanism (which adjusts the uplink power P_k ¹⁸
¹⁹according to the slow propagation losses L_k at every device).¹⁹
²⁰

²¹ The BS combines the received signals in a CP of R time slots to perform multi-user²¹
²²detection. We assume that the channel is constant on one time slot but uncorrelated²²
²³between time slots (fast fading channel assumption)^[8]. Accordingly, assuming that²³
²⁴ \tilde{k} devices are present, the received signal in a CP can be arranged in vector form²⁴
²⁵by separating the real and imaginary parts as (see [37, Sect. 7.1]):²⁵

$$\mathbf{y} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{y}_R \end{bmatrix} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma \sigma_w^2}{2M}} \bar{\mathbf{H}} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{w} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma \sigma_w^2}{2M}} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{H}}_{1,1} & \dots & \bar{\mathbf{H}}_{\tilde{k},1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \bar{\mathbf{H}}_{1,R} & \dots & \bar{\mathbf{H}}_{\tilde{k},R} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_{\tilde{k}} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{w}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{w}_R \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

³¹ where $\mathbf{y}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{2NT \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{w}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{2NT \times 1}$ contain the real and imaginary parts of the³¹
³²received signal and the noise samples in the r -th time slot (see (2)), $\mathbf{x}_k =$ ³²
³³ $[\alpha_{k,1} \dots \alpha_{k,Q} \beta_{k,1} \dots \beta_{k,Q}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2Q \times 1}$ contains the $2Q$ real and imaginary parts of³³
³⁴

³⁵^[7]Note that LTE uses QPSK, 16-QAM, and 64-QAM [6], while NB-IoT does only support QPSK³⁵
^[11].

³⁶^[8]If the channel was static and constant among time slots, then the fast fading channel assumption³⁶
³⁷could be achieved by ensuring that each terminal adds a different random phase for transmission³⁷
in every time slot.

¹the complex symbols transmitted by the k -th device (see (1)), and $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_{k,r} \in \mathbb{R}^{2NT \times 2Q}$
²denotes the equivalent channel matrix for the k -th device during the r -th time
³slot. The equivalent channel matrix $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_{k,r}$ depends on the Rayleigh flat-fading chan-
⁴nel matrix ($\mathbf{H}_{k,r}$ in (2)) and the pair of real-valued code matrices ($\mathbf{A}_q, \mathbf{B}_q$ in (1))
⁵(see details in [33, Appendix]). According to this, $\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^{2NTR \times 1}$, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{2Q\tilde{k} \times 1}$, and
⁶ $\bar{\mathbf{H}} \in \mathbb{R}^{2NTR \times 2Q\tilde{k}}$.

⁷Note that to perform decoding of the contending signals, the receiver (BS) has
⁸to get the identity of the contending devices to estimate the channel matrices from
⁹them. In this regard, we assume that all devices have orthogonal pilot signals and
¹⁰that channels are perfectly acquired at the receiver side. The effect of a limited
¹¹number of orthogonal pilot signals, non-orthogonal pilot signals, and imperfectly
¹²acquired channels, is out of the scope of the paper and is left as interesting future
¹³work.

¹⁵2.2.2 Packet Error Rate ¹⁵

¹⁶By using a decorrelating receiver at the BS that combines the repetitions of devices
¹⁷attempting transmission within a CP of R time slots (see (3)), the multiple access
¹⁸interference is vanished and the bit error rate (BER) is invariant to the amplitudes
¹⁹of the interfering signals [33]. Therefore, for m -QAM, the BER of device k given
²⁰that \tilde{k} devices are transmitting is given by [40, 41]:
²¹

$$\text{BER}_{\tilde{k},k} = \frac{4\left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{m}}\right)}{\log_2(m)} \mathcal{Q}\left(\sqrt{\frac{3\chi_{\tilde{k},k}\gamma}{2M(m-1)}}\right), \quad \forall \tilde{k} \leq K, \quad (4)$$

²⁵where $\mathcal{Q}(\cdot)$ refers to the Q-function (the integral of a Gaussian density) and $\chi_{\tilde{k},k}$
²⁶is a chi-square distributed random variable with $\text{dof}_{\tilde{k}}$ degrees of freedom for any
²⁷OSTBC with $M=T$:

$$\text{dof}_{\tilde{k}} = 2(RNM - Q\tilde{k} + Q). \quad (5)$$

³¹For 4-QAM (QPSK), the BER expression in (4) is reduced to: $\text{BER}_{\tilde{k},k} = \mathcal{Q}\left(\sqrt{\frac{\chi_{\tilde{k},k}\gamma}{2M}}\right)$.
³²In case that m -PSK was considered, the BER expression in (4) should be modified
³³according to [40] and the whole forthcoming analysis would apply as well.

³⁴In (4) we have assumed fixed power spent at devices per time slot. This will allow
³⁵us to compare the FF-NDMA protocol with classical NDMA [18] and H-NDMA [31],
³⁶in which constant power per time slot is used since devices do not know the number
³⁷of repetitions to be performed until a collision occurs and the BS communicates so.

¹ Note that while R is a value to be fixed by the network, the value of \tilde{k} is random¹
² in each CP and depends on K , σ , and v . So, the BER in a CP depends not only on²
³ the average SNR (γ) but also on the actual number of devices that are transmitting³
⁴ (\tilde{k}).⁴

⁵ As in [33], we assume that a packet is in error whenever the BER in (4)⁶
⁷ is above a certain threshold ω . Therefore, an upper bound of the packet error⁷
⁸ rate (PER) for device k given that \tilde{k} devices are transmitting can be found as:⁸
⁹ $\text{PER}_{\tilde{k},k} \leq \Pr(\text{BER}_{\tilde{k},k} \geq \omega)$. According to this and (4), we get:⁹

$$\text{PER}_{\tilde{k},k} \leq \Pr\left(\sqrt{\chi_{\tilde{k},k}} \leq \mathcal{Q}^{-1}\left(\frac{\omega \log_2(m)}{4(1-\frac{1}{\sqrt{m}})}\right) \sqrt{\frac{2M(m-1)}{3\gamma}}\right), \quad (6)$$

¹³ which can be computed according to the cumulative function of the chi distribution¹³
¹⁴ in closed-form as:¹⁴

$$\text{PER}_{\tilde{k},k} \leq 1 - F_{\tilde{k}}\left(\mathcal{Q}^{-1}\left(\frac{\omega \log_2(m)}{4(1-\frac{1}{\sqrt{m}})}\right) \sqrt{\frac{2M(m-1)}{3\gamma}}\right), \quad (7)$$

¹⁸ where¹⁸

$$F_{\tilde{k}}(z) = e^{-z^2/2} \sum_{l=0}^I \frac{(z^2/2)^l}{l!}, \quad I = \frac{\text{dof}_{\tilde{k}}}{2} - 1. \quad (8)$$

²³ It is important to recall that, as γ is equal for all devices, distinction among²³
²⁴ specific devices is not necessary and the following condition is fulfilled (see (7)):²⁴

$$\text{PER}_{\tilde{k}} = \text{PER}_{\tilde{k},k} = \text{PER}_{\tilde{k},j}, \quad \forall j, k. \quad (9)$$

²⁸ 3 Markov Model for FF-NDMA²⁸

³⁰ Analytic characterization of the performance and stability of the FF-NDMA proto-³⁰
³¹ col with MPR requires the use of a Markov model that incorporates different states³¹
³² of the system and the transition probabilities between them. In this regard, in this³²
³³ section we first set up the MPR model for the FF-NDMA protocol, which will allow³³
³⁴ us to work with conditional probabilities instead of associating collisions or erro-³⁴
³⁵ neous receptions to deterministic failures. Then, according to the MPR model, we³⁵
³⁶ derive analytic expressions for the system state probabilities of the finite Markov³⁶
³⁷ chain that represents the FF-NDMA protocol.³⁷

3.1 MPR Matrix

The MPR model is characterized by an MPR matrix that contains conditional probabilities, see [14]. Under FF-NDMA, the MPR matrix $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{\tilde{R} \times (\tilde{R}+1)}$ with $\tilde{R} = NR$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{1,0} & C_{1,1} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ C_{2,0} & C_{2,1} & C_{2,2} & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & & & \ddots & \vdots \\ C_{\tilde{R},0} & C_{\tilde{R},1} & C_{\tilde{R},2} & \cdots & C_{\tilde{R},\tilde{R}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

where $C_{x,y}$, $1 \leq x \leq \tilde{R}$, $0 \leq y \leq x$, denotes the probability that, given x transmitting devices, y out of x transmissions are successful. The number of non-zero rows of the MPR matrix is given by the maximum number of packets that can be simultaneously decoded, i.e. \tilde{R} .

As γ is assumed equal for all K devices, we do not need to distinguish among specific devices so that the element $C_{x,y}$ of the MPR matrix \mathbf{C} contains the product of PERs corresponding to the combinations of x devices for which y transmissions are successful and $x-y$ are not. According to (9), the elements of the MPR matrix in (10) (i.e. $C_{x,y}$ for $1 \leq x \leq \tilde{R}$, $0 \leq y \leq x$) are given by:

$$C_{x,y} = \binom{x}{y} (\text{PER}_x)^{x-y} (1 - \text{PER}_x)^y, \quad (11)$$

and $C_{x,y} = 0$ for $y > x$. Thus, we can complete the MPR matrix that characterizes the FF-NDMA protocol, \mathbf{C} in (10), using (7), (9), and (11).

3.2 Markov Chain for the System States

Let random variable $B(s)$ denote the number of backlogged devices at the beginning of CP s . $B(s)$ is referred to as the *system state*, which depends on the previous system state (i.e. $B(s-1)$) as well as on the number of devices whose state has changed during CP s . Hence, the process can be modeled by a finite Markov chain since $B(s) \leq K$. Fig. 4 shows the Markov chain for a simplified scenario with $K=3$.

The steady-state probability of the system being in state i (π_i) is thus given by:

$$\pi_i = \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} \Pr(B(s) = i), \quad (12)$$

¹and the transition probability from system state i to j ($p_{ij}, 0 \leq i, j \leq K$) is defined¹
²as [42]:²

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{3} & & \text{3} \\
 & \text{4} & p_{i,j} = \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} \Pr(B(s) = j | B(s-1) = i). & (13) \text{4} \\
 & \text{5} & & \text{5}
 \end{aligned}$$

⁶Notice that, under conventional slotted ALOHA, downward transitions are only⁶
⁷possible from system state i to $j=i-1$, since a single packet can be decoded at a⁷
⁸time, and $p_{0,1}=0$. In contrast, under FF-NDMA, downward transitions are possible⁸
⁹from system state i to $j \leq i - \tilde{R}$ as long as $j \geq 0$. In Fig. 4 all downward transitions have⁹
¹⁰been represented; however, only those from system state i to $j \leq i - \tilde{R}$ are possible,¹⁰
¹¹i.e. are such that $p_{i,j} \neq 0$.¹¹

¹²
¹³
¹⁴
¹⁵ Now we focus on obtaining the transition probabilities $p_{i,j}$ in (13), which depend¹⁵
¹⁶on the MPR matrix \mathbf{C} in (10), the generation probability σ , and the retransmission¹⁶
¹⁷probability ν . To do so, let us define the following parameters.¹⁷

¹⁸
¹⁹
²⁰
²¹ Define $\phi_i^{m,n}$ as the probability that $m \geq 0$ backlogged devices transmit and $n \geq 0$ new²¹
²²packets are generated by thinking devices given that the system state is i (i.e. there²²
²³are i devices in the backlog and $K-i$ devices in the thinking state). Since packet²³
²⁴generation and packet retransmission are independent events, $\phi_i^{m,n}$ is obtained as:²⁴
²⁵

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{26} & & \text{26} \\
 & \text{27} & \phi_i^{m,n} = \binom{i}{m} \nu^m (1-\nu)^{i-m} \binom{K-i}{n} \sigma^n (1-\sigma)^{K-i-n}. & (14) \text{27} \\
 & \text{28} & & \text{28}
 \end{aligned}$$

²⁹
³⁰
³¹
³² Similarly, define $\varphi_i^{m,n}$ as the probability that more than m backlogged devices³²
³³transmit and $n \geq 0$ new packets are generated by thinking devices given that the³³
³⁴system state is i :³⁴

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{35} & & \text{35} \\
 & \text{36} & & \text{36} \\
 & \text{37} & \varphi_i^{m,n} = \left(1 - \sum_{l=0}^m \binom{i}{l} \nu^l (1-\nu)^{i-l} \right) \binom{K-i}{n} \sigma^n (1-\sigma)^{K-i-n}. & (15) \text{37}
 \end{aligned}$$

¹ This way, the transition probabilities $p_{i,j}$ in (13) for $i-\tilde{R} \leq j \leq i+\tilde{R}$ can be found by¹
² performing the following operation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \begin{bmatrix} p_{i,i-\tilde{R}} \\ \vdots \\ p_{i,i-2} \\ p_{i,i-1} \\ p_{i,i} \\ p_{i,i+1} \\ p_{i,i+2} \\ \vdots \\ p_{i,i+\tilde{R}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \phi_i^{1,0} \\ \phi_i^{1,0} & \phi_i^{0,1} \\ \phi_i^{0,1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_{1,0} \\ C_{1,1} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \phi_i^{2,0} \\ 0 & \phi_i^{2,0} & \phi_i^{1,1} \\ \phi_i^{2,0} & \phi_i^{1,1} & \phi_i^{0,2} \\ \phi_i^{1,1} & \phi_i^{0,2} & 0 \\ \phi_i^{0,2} & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_{2,0} \\ C_{2,1} \\ C_{2,2} \end{bmatrix} + \dots \\
 & + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \phi_i^{\tilde{R},0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \phi_i^{\tilde{R}-1,1} \\ 0 & 0 & \phi_i^{\tilde{R}-2,2} \\ 0 & \phi_i^{\tilde{R},0} & \vdots \\ \phi_i^{\tilde{R},0} & \phi_i^{\tilde{R}-1,1} & \phi_i^{0,\tilde{R}} \\ \phi_i^{\tilde{R}-1,1} & \phi_i^{\tilde{R}-2,2} & 0 \\ \phi_i^{\tilde{R}-2,2} & \vdots & \phi_i^{0,\tilde{R}} \\ \vdots & \phi_i^{0,\tilde{R}} & \vdots \\ \phi_i^{0,\tilde{R}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_{\tilde{R},0} \\ C_{\tilde{R},1} \\ C_{\tilde{R},2} \\ \vdots \\ C_{\tilde{R},\tilde{R}} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \phi_i^{0,0} + \varphi_i^{\tilde{R},0} \\ \varphi_i^{\tilde{R}-1,1} \\ \varphi_i^{\tilde{R}-2,2} \\ \vdots \\ \varphi_i^{0,\tilde{R}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)
 \end{aligned}$$

²³ The left-hand-side vector in (16) includes all transition probabilities from system²³
²⁴ state i to states in between $i-\tilde{R}$ and $i+\tilde{R}$.

²⁵ For illustrative purposes, let us explain how, for instance, $p_{i,i}$ in (16) is computed²⁵
²⁶ (i.e. the probability of remaining in state i). Then, by taking each row of the MPR²⁶
²⁷ matrix, we consider all the possible cases where from 1 to \tilde{R} packets are transmit-²⁷
²⁸ ted. The first right-hand-side matrix product takes into account the case where 1²⁸
²⁹ packet is transmitted. In this case two events can happen: a backlogged packet is²⁹
³⁰ transmitted but it is not successfully decoded ($\phi_i^{1,0} C_{1,0}$), or a new packet is gen-³⁰
³¹ erated and it is successfully decoded ($\phi_i^{0,1} C_{1,1}$). In both situations the state of the³¹
³² backlog does not change. The rest of terms in (16) account for the cases in which³²
³³ 2, 3, ..., \tilde{R} packets were transmitted, and we have obtained them by extrapolating³³
³⁴ the aforementioned reasoning. In this particular case, where the system state i re-³⁴
³⁵ mains unchanged, the probability of not transmitting any packet (i.e. $\phi_i^{0,0}$) as well³⁵
³⁶ as the case where more than \tilde{R} backlogged packets are transmitted (i.e. $\varphi_i^{\tilde{R},0}$) have³⁶
³⁷ to be considered (see last right-hand-side vector in (16)).

¹associated throughput on each state (S_i), i.e.:

$$S = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{i=0}^K S_i \pi_i \text{ [packets/slot]}, \quad (18)$$

⁵where the $\frac{1}{R}$ penalty arises because devices do repeat the same packet R times
⁶within the CP. S_i in (18) denotes the throughput obtained in system state i and
⁷considers the different cases where successful decoding takes place (i.e. the elements
⁸of the MPR matrix $C_{x,y}$ such that $1 \leq x \leq \tilde{R}$ and $1 \leq y \leq x$, each with its associated
⁹throughput of y successfully decoded packets):

$$S_i = \sum_{x=1}^{\tilde{R}} \sum_{y=1}^x y C_{x,y} \sum_{m+n=x} \phi_i^{m,n}, \quad (19)$$

¹⁴where $\sum_{m+n=x} \phi_i^{m,n}$ denotes the probability that exactly x packets are transmitted,
¹⁵(which can come from backlog and/or thinking states). For example, with $\tilde{R}=2$, the
¹⁶throughput associated to each system state (S_i in (19), $i=0, \dots, K$) results:

$$S_i = C_{1,1}(\phi_i^{0,1} + \phi_i^{1,0}) + C_{2,1}(\phi_i^{1,1} + \phi_i^{2,0} + \phi_i^{0,2}) + 2C_{2,2}(\phi_i^{1,1} + \phi_i^{2,0} + \phi_i^{0,2}). \quad (20)$$

²⁰4.2 Delay ²⁰

²¹The mean delay (D) is the average number of time slots required for a successful
²²packet transmission, which includes the mean backlog delay, the duration of packet
²³transmission, and the waiting time until a transmission opportunity (i.e. CP start).
²⁴

²⁵To derive D, we first compute the mean backlog delay, i.e. the mean time a device
²⁶spends in the backlog [42], as follows. Let \bar{B} denote the mean number of devices in
²⁷the backlog that is simply given by:

$$\bar{B} = \sum_{i=0}^K i \pi_i. \quad (21)$$

³¹If devices join the backlog at a rate b , by using Little's formula [44], the mean time
³²spent in the backlog is \bar{B}/b .

³³A fraction $(S-b)/S$ of the packets are never backlogged and thus have a $(3R-1)/2$
³⁴mean delay, which comes from the duration of a packet transmission (i.e. R time
³⁵slots) plus the mean waiting time until the CP starts (i.e. $(R-1)/2$). Contrarily, the
³⁶packets whose fraction is b/S will experience the mean backlog delay (i.e. \bar{B}/b) plus
³⁷a $(3R-1)/2$ delay.

¹ Therefore, the mean delay D (measured in number of time slots) is given by the ¹
² weighted sum of delays associated to packets that are never backlogged and packets ²
³ that are backlogged: ³

$$D = \left(\frac{S-b}{S}\right)\left(\frac{3R-1}{2}\right) + \frac{b}{S}\left(\frac{\bar{B}}{b} + \frac{3R-1}{2}\right) = \frac{(3R-1)}{2} + \frac{\bar{B}}{S} \text{ [slots]}. \quad (22)$$

⁷ Note that although b has been defined to derive D , the final expression of D in (22) ⁷
⁸ does not depend on it. ⁸

¹⁰ 4.3 Capture Probability ¹⁰

¹¹ The capture probability (P^{cap}) is the probability of a successful packet transmission ¹¹
¹² given that a packet has been transmitted. It measures the reliability of the trans- ¹²
¹³ mission scheme [4]. P^{cap} can be computed by considering the weighted average for ¹³
¹⁴ all system states of the probability that the transmission is successful given that a ¹⁴
¹⁵ packet is transmitted and the system state is i (i.e. P_i^{cap}): ¹⁵

$$P^{\text{cap}} = \sum_{i=0}^K \pi_i P_i^{\text{cap}}. \quad (23)$$

¹⁹ P_i^{cap} is obtained by considering all the cases where a successful transmission takes ¹⁹
²⁰ place (i.e. $\tilde{k}=1, \dots, \tilde{R}$). In each case, it is given by the product of the probability ²⁰
²¹ of a successful decoding given that \tilde{k} devices transmit (i.e. $(1 - \text{PER}_{\tilde{k}})$) times the ²¹
²² probability that $\tilde{k}-1$ devices transmit (i.e. $\sum_{m+n=\tilde{k}-1} \phi_i^{m,n}$). Thus, it results to be: ²²
²³

$$P_i^{\text{cap}} = \sum_{\tilde{k}=1}^{\tilde{R}} (1 - \text{PER}_{\tilde{k}}) \sum_{m+n=\tilde{k}-1} \phi_i^{m,n}, \quad (24)$$

²⁷ where $\text{PER}_{\tilde{k}}$ is shown in (9). ²⁷

²⁹ 4.4 Energy ²⁹

³⁰ To compute the mean energy consumption (E) for a successfully packet transmis- ³⁰
³¹ sion, we consider that each device can be in four different device states (being each ³¹
³² one associated with a different power consumption level: P_0, P_1, P_2, P_3 , measured ³²
³³ in Watts) (see Fig. 3): ³³

- ³⁴ • *thinking* (or idle) state (P_0): there is no data to transmit, ³⁴
- ³⁵ • *transmitting* state (P_1): the device is transmitting, ³⁵
- ³⁶ • *decoding* state (P_2): the device is listening to the BS signaling and decoding ³⁶
³⁷ the acknowledgment, or ³⁷

- 1 • *waiting* state (P_3): there is a packet to transmit but there is no transmission¹
2 opportunity^[9].²

3 For FF-NDMA, the mean number of time slots that a device spends on every³
4 device state (T_0, T_1, T_2, T_3) is:⁴

$$5 \quad T_0 = 1/\sigma, \quad T_1 = \tau RN_{\text{tx}}, \quad T_2 = (1 - \tau)N_{\text{tx}}, \quad T_3 = D - T_1 - T_2. \quad (25)^6$$

8 The number of time slots in the thinking state (T_0) is given by the inverse of the⁸
9 packet generation probability (σ). The number of time slots for the transmitting⁹
10 state (T_1) depends on the number of transmissions required for a successful trans-¹⁰
11 mission (denoted by N_{tx} , and given in next equation (26)), the fact that within a¹¹
12 CP the packet is repeated R times, and the fraction of a time slot that is devoted for¹²
13 data transmission (τ). For the decoding state, T_2 depends on N_{tx} and the fraction of¹³
14 a time slot that is reserved to receive feedback from the BS ($1 - \tau$). Recall that only¹⁴
15 one decoding per CP in which a packet was transmitted is needed in FF-NDMA.¹⁵
16 Finally, The number of time slots in the waiting state (T_3) is determined by the¹⁶
17 average delay D in (22) minus the mean transmitting and decoding times, hence¹⁷
18 including the waiting time in the backlog and the waiting time for the CP to start.¹⁸
19 The number of transmissions required for a successful transmission (N_{tx} in (25))¹⁹
20 is given by the inverse of the capture probability P_{cap} shown in (23):²⁰

$$22 \quad N_{\text{tx}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} nP^{\text{cap}}(1 - P^{\text{cap}})^{n-1} = \frac{1}{P^{\text{cap}}}. \quad (26)^{22}$$

24 Note that the number of transmissions in (26) does not consider the number of²⁴
25 repetitions within a CP, it is rather given by the number of times the device accesses²⁵
26 the channel.²⁶

27 Therefore, the mean consumed energy E (measured in Watts \times slot) is given by the²⁷
28 product of the time that devices spend on each state by the power spent on each²⁸
29 device state:²⁹

$$31 \quad E = T_0P_0 + T_1P_1 + T_2P_2 + T_3P_3 \text{ [Watts} \times \text{slots]}. \quad (27)^{31}$$

33 4.5 Energy Efficiency³³

34 The energy efficiency (EE) is a benefit-cost ratio that measures the efficiency of³⁴
35 a protocol [45]. It is defined as the amount of data (benefit) that can be reliably³⁵
36 transmitted.³⁶

^[9]The waiting time includes the waiting time in the backlog as well as the waiting time for the³⁷
37 CP to start.³⁷

¹transmitted per Joule of consumed energy (cost). Thus, it is measured in bits/Joule¹
²or, equivalently, in packets/slot/Watt (according to the definitions in previous sec-²
³tions). The energy efficiency is a highly relevant metric in low-powered and finite³
⁴battery lifetime MTC devices [4].⁴

⁵ Based on the model presented in Section 4.4, the mean power consumption for a⁵
⁶successful packet transmission (measured in Watts) is given by:⁶

$$\begin{aligned} \text{P} &= \frac{T_0 P_0 + T_1 P_1 + T_2 P_2 + T_3 P_3}{T_0 + T_1 + T_2 + T_3} = \frac{E}{T_0 + D} \text{ [Watts]}. \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

¹⁰ Accordingly, EE (in packets/slot/Watt) is given by the ratio between the through-¹⁰
¹¹put S in (18) and the mean consumed power P in (28):¹¹

$$\text{EE} = \frac{S}{P} = \frac{S}{E} (T_0 + D) \text{ [packets/slot/Watt]}. \quad (29)$$

¹⁵ Note that the energy efficiency EE captures the trade-offs in throughput and energy¹⁵
¹⁶consumption that might arise with different NDMA-based protocols.¹⁶

¹⁹4.6 Stability Criteria¹⁹

²⁰Stability analysis is usually performed for infinite-user random access (see [14]) or²⁰
²¹for finite-user buffered random access (see [46] and references therein), where devices²¹
²²are equipped with a buffer of infinite size. In the former case, the system is unstable²²
²³when the number of devices in the backlog grows to infinity while, in the later, the²³
²⁴system is unstable when the buffer size grows to infinity.²⁴

²⁵ For finite-user random access with single packet buffer, stability has not been²⁵
²⁶defined. However, it can be addressed if a sensible definition related to undesired²⁶
²⁷states of the system is done. In this sense, we here set two stability criteria for²⁷
²⁸finite-user random access with single packet buffer.²⁸

- ²⁹ • Stability based on the probability of being in the last system state. The system²⁹
³⁰is said to be stable if the probability of being in system state K is below a³⁰
³¹certain threshold, i.e. if³¹

$$\pi_K \leq \alpha, \quad (30)$$

³⁵ where $0 < \alpha < 1$.³⁵

- ³⁶ • Stability based on the mean number of devices that are in the backlog. The³⁶
³⁷system is said to be stable if the mean number of devices in the backlog is³⁷

1 below a certain threshold, i.e. if

2

$$3 \quad \bar{B} \leq \beta, \quad (31)$$

4

5 with $0 < \beta < K$.

6

7 **5 Results and System Design Clues**

8 In this section we evaluate the FF-NDMA protocol in terms of throughput, delay,

9 capture probability, energy, and energy efficiency so as to devise the most suitable

10 CP length (R) as a function of the the offered load ($G=\sigma K$) and the SNR (γ). $K=30$

11 devices are considered. A symmetric scenario with an equal average SNR (i.e. γ)

12 for all devices is used. γ is determined by devices in worst propagation conditions,

13 and so γ will be varied through simulations to emulate the different propagation

14 conditions. The retransmission probability is set equal to the generation probability:

15 i.e. $v=\sigma$.

16 The 2×2 MIMO with Alamouti OSTBC is considered (i.e. 2 antennas at devices

17 and 2 antennas at BS, $M=N=T=Q=2$). The transmitted symbols are QPSK (i.e.

18 $m=4$ in (4)). The BER threshold is equal to $\omega=0.001$. For the power consumption,

19 $P_0=0.01$ mW, $P_1=200$ mW (i.e. 23 dBm as transmit power at devices), $P_2=150$ mW,

20 $P_3=10$ mW, and $\tau = 0.8$ are used (according to [47] and [48]).

21 The performance of FF-NDMA is compared to classical slotted ALOHA (S-

22 ALOHA), classical NDMA [18], and H-NDMA [31], all with MIMO configurations.

23 S-ALOHA corresponds to the case of $R=1$. To emulate NDMA and H-NDMA under

24 the same conditions, the proposed framework in this work can be applied with some

25 slight but important modifications. For H-NDMA, we denote as R_h the number of

26 additional repetitions that the BS may request on a HARQ basis. As compared to

27 NDMA, this reduces the PER but might increase the energy consumed in devices

28 for data decoding. For simulations, we use up to $R_h=4$. Therefore, the modifications

29 required to emulate NDMA and H-NDMA are:

- 30 • The degrees of freedom $\text{dof}_{\tilde{k}}$ in (5) are equal to:

31

$$32 \quad \text{NDMA :} \quad \text{dof}_{\tilde{k}} = 2 \left(\left\lceil \frac{\tilde{k}}{N} \right\rceil NM - Q\tilde{k} + Q \right),$$

$$33 \quad \text{H-NDMA :} \quad \text{dof}_{\tilde{k}} = 2 \left(\left(\left\lceil \frac{\tilde{k}}{N} \right\rceil + R_h \right) NM - Q\tilde{k} + Q \right), \quad (32)$$

34

35 since the number of repetitions is adjusted at each collision according to the

36 number of collided packets \tilde{k} . H-NDMA might have more degrees of freedom

37 than NDMA, and thus a lower PER (see (7)), which is beneficial at low SNR.

1 • NDMA and H-NDMA protocols can (ideally) decode $\tilde{R}=\tilde{k}$ packets (i.e. all col-¹
 2 lided packets)^[10] by setting $\lceil \frac{\tilde{k}}{N} \rceil - 1$ repetitions in NDMA and up to $\lceil \frac{\tilde{k}}{N} \rceil - 1 + R_h$ ²
 3 repetitions in H-NDMA. Therefore, the MPR matrix \mathbf{C} in (10) has a size of³
 4 $K \times (K+1)$, since collisions of up to K devices can be resolved in both proto-⁴
 5 cols.⁵

6 • The throughput S for NDMA and H-NDMA can be computed as follows:⁶

$$7 \quad S = \frac{1}{l} \sum_{i=0}^K S_i \pi_i, \quad (33)^8$$

10 where l is the average number of repetitions:¹⁰

$$11 \quad l = \sum_{i=0}^K l_i \pi_i, \quad l_i = \sum_{m=0}^i \sum_{n=0}^{K-i} (m+n) \phi_i^{m,n}. \quad (34)^{12}$$

14 • The mean delays D are:¹⁴

$$15 \quad \begin{aligned} \text{NDMA :} \quad D &= \frac{(3l-1)}{2} + \frac{\bar{B}}{S}, \\ \text{H-NDMA :} \quad D &= \frac{(3(l+R_h)-1)}{2} + \frac{\bar{B}}{S}. \end{aligned} \quad (35)^{17}$$

19 • The mean energy consumption E in (27) is also dependent on the average¹⁹
 20 number of repetitions in (34), as l impacts on the mean transmitting, decoding,²⁰
 21 and waiting times:²¹

$$22 \quad T_1 = \tau l N_{\text{tx}}, \quad T_2 = (1 - \tau)D, \quad T_3 = D - T_1 - T_2. \quad (36)^{23}$$

25 Note that, in NDMA and H-NDMA, decoding of control signaling from the BS at²⁵
 26 devices is required in every time slot, as shown in Fig. 2. This is reflected in T_2 ,²⁶
 27 see (36). Conversely, with FF-NDMA, decoding is needed per CP (i.e. 1 decoding²⁷
 28 every R time slots) to receive ACK only at those CPs in which a packet has been²⁸
 29 transmitted (see T_2 in (25)).²⁹

30 Finally, in order to take into account practical implementation issues, we define³⁰
 31 parameter d_{retx} as the delay (in number of time slots) between reception of feedback³¹
 32 and the next repetition in NDMA and H-NDMA protocols (see explanation in³²
 33 Section 2.1). In the ideal case, $d_{\text{retx}}=0$. Otherwise, delay in (35) is modified as³³
 34 follows: $D_{\text{retx}}=D+(l-1)d_{\text{retx}}$, i.e. each repetition has an associated delay of d_{retx} ³⁴
 35 time slots. In this case, the mean waiting time is given by: $T_3=D_{\text{retx}}-T_1-T_2$. So, the³⁵
 36 mean waiting time T_3 increases as d_{retx} increases. For simulations, we consider the³⁶

37^[10] Recall that, in FF-NDMA, the BS can decode at most $\tilde{R}=RN$ packets at each CP.³⁷

¹ideal case with $d_{\text{retx}}=0$ and the case of $d_{\text{retx}}=4$ (which do affect the delay and energy¹
²metrics of NDMA and H-NDMA).²

³

⁴4.5.1 Performance⁴

⁵In this section we evaluate the FF-NDMA protocol in terms of throughput (S),⁵
⁶delay (D), capture probability (P^{cap}), and energy (E), by following the expressions⁶
⁷in (18), (22), (23) and (27), respectively, as a function of the offered load ($G=\sigma K$)⁷
⁸for an average SNR (γ) of 10 dB and 0 dB under different R values (indicated in⁸
⁹the legends). Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show the performance results for $\gamma=10$ dB and $\gamma=0$ ⁹
¹⁰dB, respectively.¹⁰

¹¹ For $\gamma=10$ dB (see Fig. 5), ideal NDMA and ideal H-NDMA with $d_{\text{retx}}=0$ provide¹¹
¹²the largest performance (in terms of throughput, energy, and delay) because they¹²
¹³are able to adapt the number of repetitions dynamically to the number of collided¹³
¹⁴packets. At medium/high SNR, H-NDMA is equivalent to NDMA, since no addi-¹⁴
¹⁵tional repetitions on a HARQ basis are required. Differently, for $\gamma=0$ dB (see Fig.¹⁵
¹⁶6), the performance of ideal NDMA vanishes because the system is limited by the¹⁶
¹⁷erroneous detections rather than by the number of collided packets. This situation¹⁷
¹⁸is resolved with ideal H-NDMA, which provides the largest performance gains (in¹⁸
¹⁹terms of throughput, energy, and delay) at low SNR when $d_{\text{retx}}=0$, since it can cope¹⁹
²⁰with the erroneous packet receptions through additional repetitions, improving as²⁰
²¹well the reliability.²¹

²²**Remark 1** *At low SNR regime, FF-NDMA outperforms ideal NDMA protocol²²*
²³($d_{\text{retx}}=0$) in terms of throughput, delay, and energy without the need of invoking²³
²⁴HARQ processes (which are needed for H-NDMA and might involve larger delays²⁴
²⁵in case a delay between the packet transmission, the feedback, and the repetition is²⁵
²⁶considered, i.e. $d_{\text{retx}}>0$).²⁶

²⁷ FF-NDMA performance can get close to ideal H-NDMA for different SNR ranges²⁷
²⁸when choosing a suitable fixed CP length according to the offered load of the system.²⁸
²⁹It can be observed that a maximum throughput level at low loads is achieved but²⁹
³⁰as the load increases the throughput diminishes (see Fig. 5.(a) and Fig. 6.(a)).³⁰
³¹This is because no backoff policy is considered at all ($v=\sigma$), and the system gets³¹
³²saturated for high offered loads. Using larger R increases the value of the maximum³²
³³throughput and its decay with the load starts later (i.e. the stability region is³³
³⁴enlarged). Hence, if σ takes high values, it might be wiser to use larger R . Also, it is³⁴
³⁵important to note that the load point in which the network should switch towards³⁵
³⁶a larger R is reduced for low SNR regions and, hence, the use of a larger CP length³⁶
³⁷starts to be relevant for lower loads (see Fig. 6.(a)). The delay and the energy grow³⁷

¹rapidly to infinity as the load increases (see Fig. 5.(b)-(d) and Fig. 6.(b)-(d)). By¹
²using larger R , the delay and energy are reduced and maintained for a wide range²
³of offered loads. The system reliability is larger with large R (see Fig. 5.(c) and Fig.³
⁴6.(c)), since a larger CP length allows improving the PER (see (5)).⁴

⁵**Remark 2** *In FF-NDMA, the optimal R for maximum throughput, minimum de-⁵
⁶lay, or minimum energy, depends on the offered load. As the load increases, higher⁶
⁷ R can provide larger throughput gains, delay reductions, and energy consumption⁷
⁸savings, due to the effective capability for packet collision resolution of FF-NDMA.⁸*

⁹**Remark 3** *In FF-NDMA, the optimal R for maximum reliability is provided with⁹
¹⁰a large R , since the system can operate in a wide range of offered loads while main-¹⁰
¹¹taining the capture probability at its maximal value.¹¹*

¹²It is important to note that, for $\gamma=10$ dB, the capture probability is improved¹²
¹³with FF-NDMA as compared to S-ALOHA, NDMA, and H-NDMA (see Fig. 5.(c)).¹³
¹⁴This is due to the fact that the additional repetitions provided by a fixed CP length¹⁴
¹⁵allow reducing the PER (see (7)) and, hence, enhancing the system reliability, i.e.¹⁵
¹⁶the probability of a successful transmission, as compared to NDMA and H-NDMA¹⁶
¹⁷in which the repetitions are set mainly to resolve collisions. Differently, for $\gamma=0$ dB,¹⁷
¹⁸the reliability with H-NDMA is also high because the HARQ mechanism starts to¹⁸
¹⁹play a key role for successful packet reception (see Fig. 6.(c)).¹⁹

²⁰Regarding the energy consumption, at medium/high SNR, FF-NDMA provides²⁰
²¹similar energy consumption levels as compared to ideal H-NDMA with $d_{\text{retx}}=0$ (see²¹
²²Fig. 5.(d)). At low SNR (see Fig. 6.(d)), the energy consumption can even be reduced²²
²³with FF-NDMA as compared to ideal H-NDMA due to the energy savings provided²³
²⁴by a lower amount of control signaling to be decoded.²⁴

²⁵**Remark 4** *The performance of FF-NDMA is not far from the ideal H-NDMA²⁵
²⁶($d_{\text{retx}}=0$) and it gets closer as the SNR is reduced, while much less signaling overhead²⁶
²⁷and implementation complexity is required. The lower control signaling to be decoded²⁷
²⁸is reflected in a reduced energy consumption of FF-NDMA as compared to ideal H-²⁸
²⁹NDMA either at low SNRs (see Fig. 6.(d)) or at high loads (see Fig. 5.(d)).²⁹*

³⁰When non-ideal feedback for the repetition process is considered (e.g. $d_{\text{retx}}=4$),³⁰
³¹the FF-NDMA protocol obtains a significantly reduced delay and lower energy³¹
³²consumption as compared to NDMA and H-NDMA schemes. The non-ideal feedback³²
³³for repetitions has a detrimental impact on delay of NDMA and H-NDMA protocols³³
³⁴at any SNR range, as shown in Fig. 5.(b) and Fig. 6.(b) for $d_{\text{retx}}=4$. Instead, FF-³⁴
³⁵NDMA is not affected by the non-ideal feedback repetition process. Thus, delay³⁵
³⁶reductions of up to 70% are obtained with FF-NDMA as compared to H-NDMA³⁶
³⁷for $d_{\text{retx}}=4$. This is because devices have to wait for repetitions with H-NDMA³⁷

1 Table 1: SNR Regions where FF-NDMA Outperforms NDMA and H-NDMA protocols. 1

2	S	D	E	P^{cap}	2
3	low SNR	low SNR	low SNR	\forall SNR	3
4	low SNR	\forall SNR	low SNR	\forall SNR	4
5		\forall SNR	low SNR	med/high SNR	5
6			low SNR	med/high SNR	6

7 while in FF-NDMA the repetition procedure is fixed to the CP length. The non-7
8 ideal feedback process also cause a reduced energy consumption with FF-NDMA as
9 compared to NDMA and H-NDMA because devices spent less time in the waiting
10 state to successfully complete a packet transmission. The energy is reduced with FF-
11 NDMA in two situations: *i*) at low SNRs (see Fig. 6.(d), for which energy savings
12 of 5%-20% are obtained) and *ii*) when the load increases at medium/high SNRs
13 (see Fig. 5.(d), for which energy savings up to 10% are reported). In both cases,
14 the additional control signaling to be decoded with H-NDMA becomes relevant in
15 terms of energy consumption because devices are active more time to successfully
16 transmit a packet. 16

17 **Remark 5** *Non-ideal feedback repetition processes (i.e. $d_{\text{retx}} > 0$) have a detrimental*
18 *effect over NDMA and H-NDMA. In this conditions, FF-NDMA provides significant*
19 *delay reductions for any SNR range and load condition. Also, energy savings are*
20 *reported at low SNR and at medium/high SNR with high load conditions.* 20

21 To summarize, Table 1 includes the SNR regions in which FF-NDMA protocol
22 outperforms the benchmarked protocols (ideal NDMA, non-ideal NDMA, ideal H-
23 NDMA, and non-ideal H-NDMA) in terms of throughput S , delay D , energy E ,
24 and capture probability P^{cap} , separately. 24

27 5.2 Energy Efficiency 27

28 In this section we evaluate the energy efficiency (EE) of FF-NDMA in (29) and of
29 ideal H-NDMA ($d_{\text{retx}}=0$) as a function of the average SNR (γ). Let us recall that,
30 at high SNR, $EE_{\text{H-NDMA}} = EE_{\text{NDMA}}$ since both approaches are equivalent. However,
31 at low SNR, $EE_{\text{H-NDMA}}$ is higher than EE_{NDMA} . For FF-NDMA, $EE_{\text{FF-NDMA}}$ is
32 computed by adopting the best R for each load and SNR condition. 32

33 Let us note that in this section we use an ideal scenario for H-NDMA (i.e. $d_{\text{retx}}=0$),
34 so all the energy efficiency gains of FF-NDMA over ideal H-NDMA that are reported
35 come due to the lower control signaling to be decoded with FF-NDMA. Note also
36 that the EE is a useful metric to capture the throughput/energy trade-offs that
37 have been observed in the previous section into a single figure of merit. 37

¹ As it was shown in Section 4.5, the energy efficiency depends on the power con-¹
²sumption levels associated to the different device states (P_0, P_1, P_2, P_3) . So, to illus-²
³trate the effect of the additional control signaling to be decoded with H-NDMA, we³
⁴use different power decoding values $P_2 = \{150, 200, 250\}$ mW while keeping fixed the⁴
⁵transmit power to $P_1 = 200$ mW. Fig. 7 displays the energy efficiency for two offered⁵
⁶load conditions $G = \{10, 18\}$ packets/slot and different power decoding values (P_2 ,⁶
⁷indicated in the legends). As it is expected, varying the P_2 value has a higher impact⁷
⁸on H-NDMA than FF-NDMA, since FF-NDMA only needs to decode ACK feedback⁸
⁹while H-NDMA needs to decode ACK feedback, feedback associated to repetitions,⁹
¹⁰and feedback related to the state of the forthcoming time slots. A larger P_2 value¹⁰
¹¹increases the power consumption and, hence, reduces the EE. 11

¹² Table 2 summarizes the SNR regions in which FF-NDMA scheme is more energy 12
¹³efficient than ideal H-NDMA protocol for the different G and P_2 values displayed in 13
¹⁴Fig. 7. By considering the interval $[-5, 5]$ dB as low SNR, $[5, 15]$ dB as medium SNR, 14
¹⁵and $[15, +\infty]$ dB as high SNR (recall we are using QPSK symbols), we can conclude 15
¹⁶the following from Fig. 7 and Table 2. FF-NDMA is more energy efficient than ideal 16
¹⁷H-NDMA at low SNR for any load condition. At medium SNR, FF-NDMA scheme 17
¹⁸obtains a higher energy efficiency as compared to ideal H-NDMA when the load is 18
¹⁹high and the decoding power is similar or larger than the transmitting power (i.e. 19
²⁰ $P_2 \geq P_1$, see Fig. 7.(b)). At high SNR, ideal H-NDMA is more energy efficient for any 20
²¹load condition because the throughput is significantly better. Therefore, we infer 21
²²that energy efficiency gains of FF-NDMA w.r.t. ideal H-NDMA are obtained in two 22
²³situations: 23

- ²⁴ 24
- ²⁵ • at low SNR and 25
- ²⁶ • at medium SNR when the load increases and P_2 is similar or larger than P_1 . 26

²⁷In both situations, the additional control signaling to be decoded with H-NDMA²⁷
²⁸(and NDMA) increases significantly the power consumption as compared to FF-²⁸
²⁹NDMA because, as more repetitions are required for a successful packet trans-²⁹
³⁰mission, the difference in the power consumption among both protocols becomes³⁰
³¹evident. This fact produces that, although the throughput of FF-NDMA is always³¹
³²lower than the one of H-NDMA, the energy efficiency can be boosted with FF-³²
³³NDMA in certain situations (see (29)). 33

³⁴**Remark 6** *The energy efficiency is improved with FF-NDMA as compared to H-³⁴*
³⁵*NDMA in the situations that more repetitions are needed to complete a packet trans-³⁵*
³⁶*mission (i.e. low SNR or medium SNR with high load) due to the lower control³⁶*
³⁷*signaling to be decoded with FF-NDMA. 37*

1 Table 2: SNR Regions where FF-NDMA is more Energy Efficient than H-NDMA for different Loads 1
 (G) and Power Decoding Values (P_2).

	G=10 packets/slot	G=18 packets/slot
$P_2 = 150$ mW	$(-\infty, 0.4]$ dB	$(-\infty, 3.3]$ dB
$P_2 = 200$ mW	$(-\infty, 1.9]$ dB	$(-\infty, 11.2]$ dB
$P_2 = 250$ mW	$(-\infty, 3.5]$ dB	$(-\infty, 20.0]$ dB

6 5.3 Stability

7 In this section we evaluate the stability of the FF-NDMA protocol by following the 7
 8 criteria proposed in Section 4.6. That is: stability based on the probability of system 8
 9 state K (π_K) and stability based on the mean number of devices in the backlog (\bar{B}). 9
 10 An average SNR (γ) of 10 dB is used. $d_{\text{retx}}=0$, $P_1=200$ mW, and $P_2=150$ mW. 10

11 Fig. 8 displays π_K as a function of the offered load ($G=\sigma K$). It can be observed 11
 12 that by increasing the CP length (i.e. R), a lower value of π_K is obtained and the 12
 13 stability region is thus expanded. For example, if the system to be stable has to 13
 14 satisfy $\pi_K \leq 0.1$ then larger values of σ are available to meet the stability condition 14
 15 by using several time slots per CP. 15

16 Fig. 9 depicts \bar{B} versus the offered load ($G=\sigma K$). Similarly as in Fig. 8, with a 16
 17 larger R , a lower value of \bar{B} is obtained and the stability region is enlarged. 17

18 **Remark 7** Using larger R , the stability region is enlarged (i.e. the system can 18
 19 operate in a wider range of generation probabilities σ without exceeding undesired 19
 20 system states). 20

21 **Remark 8** By increasing the offered load (i.e. σ) or by imposing stricter stability 21
 22 criteria (i.e. lower α in (30) or lower β in (31)), stability can not be meet with low 22
 23 R and thus increasing R is the only option. 23
 24 24

25 5.4 Impact of antenna configurations

26 Finally, we analyze the impact of different antenna configurations. Different cases 26
 27 are considered to assess the importance of transmit and receive diversity through 27
 28 multi-antenna terminals: 1×1 (i.e. $M=N=T=Q=1$), 1×2 (i.e. $M=T=Q=1$ and $N=2$), 28
 29 2×2 MIMO with Alamouti OSTBC (i.e. $M=N=T=Q=2$), and 2×4 MIMO with Alam- 29
 30 outi OSTBC (i.e. $M=T=Q=2$ and $N=4$). Fig. 10 shows the energy efficiency of FF- 30
 31 NDMA in (29) and of ideal H-NDMA ($d_{\text{retx}}=0$) as a function of the average SNR (γ) 31
 32 for $G=10$ packets/slot, $P_1=200$ mW, $P_2=150$ mW. It can be observed that equipping 32
 33 the BS with multiple antennas and exploiting receive diversity provides more EE 33
 34 gains than employing multiple antennas at devices. This is because the capability 34
 35 for collision resolution at the BS linearly increases with the number of receive an- 35
 36 tennas, and so does the maximum throughput, while transmit diversity is already 36
 37 provided by the temporal repetitions. 37

16 Conclusions

2 The FF-NDMA protocol uses packet repetitions during a fixed CP to resolve colli- 2
 3 sions. The goal of this paper is to characterize it analytically from a cellular network 3
 4 perspective. To this goal, a finite-user slotted random access is considered, in which 4
 5 devices can be in one of four possible device states: transmitting, thinking, decod- 5
 6 ing, or backlogged. In this context, we characterize the system through an MPR 6
 7 model and a finite Markov chain, and derive accordingly analytic expressions for 7
 8 throughput, delay, capture probability (or reliability), energy, and energy efficiency. 8
 9

10 Results show that by increasing the CP length, the throughput is reduced and en- 10
 11 ergy/delay are increased at low loads because redundant repetitions are performed. 11
 12 In contrast, at medium/high loads, throughput, delay, and energy are improved 12
 13 with a larger CP length due to the effective capability of FF-NDMA to resolve col- 13
 14 lisions. Also, it is shown that using a larger CP length allows improving the system 14
 15 reliability and enlarging the stability region, thus enabling operation in a wider 15
 16 range of loads without exceeding undesired system states. 16

17 Results also evidence that FF-NDMA offers significant benefits as compared to 17
 18 NDMA and H-NDMA protocols in MTC-based use cases. It outperforms NDMA in 18
 19 all metrics at low SNR. As compared to ideal H-NDMA, FF-NDMA is more energy 19
 20 efficient in two situations: 1) at low SNR and 2) at medium SNR when the load 20
 21 increases and the decoding power is similar or larger than the transmitting power 21
 22 at devices, due to the lower amount of control signaling to be decoded. When non- 22
 23 ideal feedback processes for repetitions are considered, FF-NDMA can boost the 23
 24 delay and energy performance of NDMA and H-NDMA owing to the feedback-free 24
 25 repetition procedure. All this demonstrates the suitability of FF-NDMA protocol 25
 26 for scenarios characterized by a large number of devices, low complexity, limited 26
 27 signaling load, low energy consumption, and high reliability. 27

28 Interesting future work includes a deep analysis of the multi-cell deployment. 28
 29 The developed framework can be applied to devices located at the cell-edge with 29
 30 symmetric SNR conditions, which could be simultaneously decoded at multiple BSs 30
 31 to exploit further receive diversity. The general case with cell-center and cell-edge 31
 32 devices (some of them with asymmetric SNR conditions towards the different BSs) 32
 33 is also left for future work. 33

36 Competing interests

37 The authors declare that they have no competing interests. 37

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Figure 2: Slotted random access for NDMA and FF-NDMA with $R=3$. In NDMA, decoding control signaling at every time slot is needed. In FF-NDMA, control signaling has to be decoded only at those CPs in which packets were transmitted.

Figure 3: State diagram of the device operation.

Figure 4: Markov chain of the system state (number of backlogged devices) in FF-NDMA protocol for $K=3$.

Figure 5: Performance vs. offered load ($G = \sigma K$) for $\gamma = 10$ dB.

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(a) $G = \sigma K = 10$ packets/slot

(b) $G = \sigma K = 18$ packets/slot

Figure 7: Energy efficiency (packets/slot/Watt) of FF-NDMA and ideal H-NDMA ($d_{\text{retx}}=0$) vs. SNR (dB) for two different offered loads (G) and different power decoding values (P_2). $P_1=200$ mW.

